

Figure S1 pH dependence of the UV/Vis-absorption spectra of the other nucleosides in this study.

Figure S2 Phosphorylation of 2'-deoxyadenosine and 2'-deoxyinosine by Pu-NPase. The reactions were performed with 2 mM nucleoside, 10 mM K_2HPO_4 , 16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Pu-NPase in 50 mM glycine buffer at pH 9 and 60 °C.

